

A Case Study of Technology Based Feedback on Students Assessment During Online Classes

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ABSTRACT: One of the essential components of the learning process is assessment. As a result, providing feedback is an important part of the evaluation process so that students can see how far the progress in learning process. Naturally, the delivery of feedback undergoes a shift when online classes, which feature a significant amount of technology use, are implemented. The main problem that this study is trying to solve is what types of oral and written corrective technology-based feedback during online lectures using technology in class. The data were derived from research that involved focus groups, interviews and content analysis. The triangulation approach was employed by the researchers to verify the accuracy of the data. The result shows that recast is the most type of oral corrective technology-based feedback that was occurred during the online class. Recast, explicit correction and repetition can be delivered directly and the students can catch what the correct version of their errors. The time allotment for giving these three types is shorter than the other three. For the clarification requests, elicitation and metalinguistic clue, the results show that these three types allowed more time allotment as the students cannot get the correct answer directly. For written corrective technology-based feedback, direct feedback was given when the students made error in the form of punctuation and typo. Moreover, for indirect feedback, it is given when the error in the form of grammar error. The indirect feedback was given with in the way of the lecturers showed the grammatical error without giving the correct version. For the last type of written corrective feedback, it is the most rarely used as the correct version was given implicitly, that will lead the students need extra time to process what is wrong and how to revise it.

KEYWORDS: feedback, online classes, corrective feedback, oral feedback, written feedback

1. INTRODUCTION

Assessment for the students in the class includes feedback, which plays a crucial role in helping students evaluate how they understand what they have learned. By giving the feedback effectively, the students will know how far they go and what next that should be done. The correct feedback-giving is necessary to help the students realize their position or “where” are in the learning process. In higher education, feedback indeed takes a crucial aspect in the success of the learning process. It is in line with Irons (2008) in which giving students feedback is a crucial component of the lecturers’ job description. Furthermore, in giving feedback, the lecturers should deliver it in suitable way in order to make the advantages of giving feedback can be useful to the students. Moreover, feedback must be thorough enough to give students enough information about their learning and should work toward bridging the gap between current and expected performance (Nicol & Macfarlane-Dick 2006).

In educational environments, pedagogical interventions and feedback are crucial components. According to some researches, it was found that students' views of feedback have a role in determining how eager the students are to accept and apply it. In addition, Lim (2020) said that students seek to offer the learner with relevant information and guide the learner's view on critical information. Feedback also direct the learner's view on key information and notify the learner about the learning progress and potential deviations from a planned learning route. Surprisingly, feedback comes not only from the lecturers itself, but also can be delivered from other subject in learning process. Feedback on learning typically comes from instructors, fellow students, friends, or oneself (Kickmeier-Rust, 2008).

In Indonesian system education, consider feedback in this style as a present the lecturer is giving to the student. In this term, the lecturer is regarded as an authority, and feedback is one-way communication between the teacher and the student intended to convey information to about the learning process. Feedback that is given to the students is usually in the form of evaluative content. The data is typically evaluative and may show the discrepancy between present performance and planned results (Askew, 2000).

This prevalent perspective on teaching and learning is consistent with how "feedback" is used on a daily basis. Moreover, the delivering of feedback must have the movement especially during the online learning process. The platform, the content, the focus of feedback is different from the one that had been used in offline classes. That is the reason why the researchers in this study try to find how it differs the feedback that is given in offline classes compare to online classes. The focus is in what written corrective feedback used by lecturers during online classes and the types of oral corrective feedback used by lecturers during online classes.

A Case Study of Technology Based Feedback on Students Assessment during Online Classes

The researchers suggest a study with the title "A CASE STUDY OF TECHNOLOGY BASED FEEDBACK ON STUDENTS ASSESSMENT DURING ONLINE CLASSES" based on the context of this research.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

According to Heinze (2016), providing students with feedback is a crucial step in helping them become autonomous learners who can monitor, assess, and manage their own learning. Feedback can be thought of or understood as the relationship between the students and the teachers, the fundamental link between teaching and learning that takes place in the classroom (Mag, 2019). Pandya (2008) asserts that feedback has the potential to: (1) increase student learning and the student experience; (2) enhance instructional policy; and (3) advance quality assurance and improvement (3). There are often two sorts of evaluation in relation to the possibility of feedback: 1. Continuous evaluation is typically done during teaching, and it can be used to track development and decide whether immediate adjustments are required. Information on the teaching environment at the moment is provided through this evaluation. 2. End evaluations are typically conducted near the end or at the conclusion of a teaching course and can be used to assess the success of the teaching-learning process, the degree to which objectives and outcomes have been met, and to help plan future instruction. The following are examples of the old and new feedback paradigms stated by Winston and Carless (2020):

Figure 2.1 Old and New Paradigms of Feedback (Source: Winston and Carless,2020)

2.1 Functions of Feedback

According to Yuan and Kim (2015), feedback serves a variety of purposes. (1) Feedback reveals whether students' replies to learning tasks were correct, the knowledge required for accurate solutions, and learning objectives. (2) Feedback can also boost students' self-assurance and willingness to learn. Instructors commend students' accomplishments in their feedback, Yuan and Kim 409 which inspires pupils.

2.2 Corrective Feedback

Corrective feedback, also known as negative feedback, error treatment, and error correction that take place in both natural and instructional settings, is the feedback that follows an inaccurate (ungrammatical) response (Sheen, 2011). Oral corrective feedback techniques and written corrective feedback strategies are two of the different sorts of corrective feedback. The following are the several categories of oral corrective feedback systems, according to Sheen (2011). A recast is a reformulation of the student's incorrect statement that includes all or part of the student's correction and is included into the ongoing dialogue. An explicit correction is a pedagogical strategy that both makes it plain to the learner that an error has been made and offers the correct form. Explicit correction with metalinguistic explanation, this entails giving both the appropriate form and a metalinguistic commentary on it. A clarification request that includes the words "sorry?," "Pardon me?," or "I don't understand what you just said" indicates that there is a problem with the learner's statement. Repetition refers to mimicking the learner's erroneous utterance either in its entirety or partially as a way of eliciting the correct form from the learner. Elicitation, a technique for promoting self-correction, is the repetition of the learner's speech up until the point when the error occurs. In contrast to (3) above, the teacher in this feedback offers a metalinguistic observation while withholding the appropriate form to encourage the learner to self-correct the problem.

Furthermore, Sheen (2011) also defined Types of Written Corrective Feedback Strategies as; direct non-metalinguistic written correction, direct metalinguistic written correction, indirect written correction (not located), indirect written correction (located), indirect written correction using error codes, indirect metalinguistic written correction, and reformulation.

2.3 Effective Feedback

Content of the feedback, timing of the feedback, dialogue through the feedback, sources of the feedback, and student follow-up are some characteristics of effective feedback. Figure 2.2 depicts the attribute of effective feedback in a diagram.

Figure 2.2 Attributes determining the effectiveness of feedback (Yuan and Kim, 2015)

Effective feedback should explain to students their learning objectives and how they might improve. This is referred to as the content of the feedback. The following details should be included in effective feedback: "Where am I going?" Where to next, "feed up," "how am I doing," and "feedback"? 'feed forward' Additionally, the type of knowledge and abilities to be gained as well as the degree of task complexity are taken into account when determining the timing for feedback. Dialogue through Feedback examines how assessors and assesses interact. Assessors and assesses must talk about the responses in order for pupils to understand the feedback.

3. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

The researchers employed a qualitative design to address the research issues. This study falls under the category of a case study, in which the researchers get the data in-depth from the source of the data. According to Ary et al. (2010:454), qualitative research is an investigation that concentrates on a specific aspect to generate a rich and comprehensive description. In addition, qualitative research, according to Cresswell (2007:73), entails the examination of a problem as it is presented through one or more cases inside a constrained framework. A phenomenon should be placed into a specified context by a bounded system.

All of the English lecturers at one of the college in Madiun who educate students from non-English departments are the study's subjects. The speaker and the students participated in the Focus Group Discussion. It was included some of the information the researchers acquired. The data were derived from research that involved focus groups, interviews and content analysis. The lecturers were the subjected to the interviews. Some of the lecturers and students participated in the focus groups. There were a number of discussions led by students, and lecturers about feedbacks that were given during the online classes. The triangulation approach was employed by the researchers to verify the accuracy of the data. To ensure the validity of the data gathered and the precision of the researchers' judgments, triangulation involves comparing the information from different sources to what is heard and seen (Fraenkel, 2009, p. 510). Triangulation was used by the researchers to verify the accuracy of the data.

The researchers utilized an interactive model to assess the data. Three steps were engaged in this analysis: data reduction, data visualization, and data verification (Miles and Huberman, 1994, p. 12 in Punch and Oancea, 2014, p. 174). The elements of data analysis (interactive model) are shown in the following figure:

Figure 3.1 Components of Data Analysis: Interactive Model (Miles and Huberman, 1994)

A Case Study of Technology Based Feedback on Students Assessment during Online Classes

Data reduction happens repeatedly when running the analysis. The initial stages involve editing, segmenting, and summarizing the data. It takes place during the middle stages through coding, memoing, and related tasks including identifying themes, clusters, and patterns. Later on, conceptualizing and explaining are used to reduce the data because coming up with abstract concepts is also a method of doing so. Information is compressed, assembled, and organized through data presentation. Due to the fact that qualitative data is frequently large, bulky, and distributed, displays are helpful at every level of the analysis. Data can be displayed in a variety of ways, including graphs, charts, networks, and many sorts of diagrams. Displays serve as the foundation for subsequent research and also indicate the stage the study has reached. Data reduction and visualization are done to make it easier to form conclusions. The last step is drawing conclusion.

4. FINDINGS

The information for this study was acquired through focus group discussion, interview and content analysis. Additionally, lecturers participated in the interview. The researchers conducted a content analysis of the students' works in the writing classes to gather information for written corrective technology-based comments.

4.1 Oral Corrective Technology Based Feedback

The result for oral corrective technology based feedback can be seen as follows. It is divided into several parts based on the types of oral technology feedback that were occurred. The first type is recast, followed by explicit correction, clarification requests, repetition, elicitation, and the last is metalinguistic clue.

Table IV.1. Types of Oral Technology Based Feedback

No	Types
1	Recast
2	Explicit correction
3	Clarification requests
4	Repetition
5	Elicitation
6	Metalinguistic clue

A recast is a reformulation of the student's incorrect statement that includes all or part of the student's correction and is included into the ongoing dialogue. The result shows that this kind of oral technology based feedback occurred. *Example 1.*
Student: How many individuals are in class?

Lecturer: How many students can you count in the class? Twenty-five folks, I guess.

Recasts can be complete (i.e., the learner reforms their entire inaccurate speech) or partial (i.e., only a portion of it is reformulated). They may also be didactic or "conversational." A didactic recast is a reformulation of the learner's mistaken statement that highlights the exact area where the error was made, whether it be partially or entirely. The reformulation in a didactic recast is driven by an instructive purpose rather than a communicative one, as in :

Example 2.

Students: She has one children.

Lecturer: Child. (Partially recast)

When there is a breakdown in communication, a conversational recast occurs. In other words, the corrector rephrases every statement made by the learner to ensure that they understood it correctly because they didn't catch it the first time. Thus, conversational recasts are driven by a communication objective.

Example 3.

Student: Hemm.

Lecturer: What?

Student: What is your height?

Lecturer: What is my height? (Recasts of conversations)

Explicit correction was also occurred during the delivering the feedback. It happened recently in speaking classes. The lecturers performed the explicit correction when the students made mistakes related to the pronunciation. The lecturers directly showed which part that was incorrect.

Example 4.

Student: and for several events (phonological error)

Lecturer: several events. We say events.

A Case Study of Technology Based Feedback on Students Assessment during Online Classes

The third type of oral technology based feedback that is occurred is clarification requests. This types of feedback was delivered when the lecturers catch some multiple errors occurred. It happened usually when the online class used virtual meeting platform such as zoom and Google meet. The example can be seen as follows:

Example 5.

Student: "Can, can I made a card on the ...for my little brother on the computer?" (multiple error)

Lecturer: Pardon?

The fourth type of feedback is repetition. It may sounds like the recast, but actually it is different. In this repetition type, the lecturer gave the correct way with the question mark in the end of the sentence.

Example 6

Student: A.... a apple.

Lecturer: An apple?

The next type is elicitation. The elicitation occurred when the students make the lexical error. It means that the students could not say the word in the English version. The lecturer rarely use this type of oral technology feedback because the limitation of the time during the virtual meeting in the online learning process. The lecturers tend to directly correct the error by giving the correct answer. The example of elicitation that was occurred can be seen as follows:

Example 7.

Student: some students "mengembangkan" (lexical error)

Lecturer: How do we say it in English?

The last type of oral technology based feedback is metalinguistic clue. It is delivered in a way when the lecturer did not give directly correct the the error, instead of doing so, the lecturer gave the questions. It was occurred in online classes but in limited quantity as the class had limitation in time allotment. The example can be seen as follow:

Example 8.

Student: Uhm, the, the elephant. The elephant grows" (phonological error)

Lecturer: Do we say the elephant?"

The summary of the types pf oral technology based feedback can be seen in the following table.

Table IV.2. Types and example of Oral Technology Based Feedback

No	Types	Examples
1	Recast	S: A egg? (Grammatical error) T: An egg. Good.
2	Explicit correction	S: and for several events (phonological error) T: several events. We say events.
3	Clarification requests	S: "Can, can I make a card on the ...formy little brother on the computer?" (Multiple error) T: Pardon?
4	Repetition	S: A.... a apple. T: An apple?
5	Elicitation	S: some students "mengembangkan" (lexical error) T: How do we say it in English?
6	Metalinguistic clue	S: Uhm, the, the elephant. The elephant grows"(phonological error) T: Do we say the elephant?"

4.2 Written Corrective Technology Based

The second type of corrective technology-based feedback which becomes the focus of the study is the written types. For this study, the researchers focus on three types of written corrective technology-based feedback namely direct feedback, indirect feedback, and metalinguistic feedback. The types can be seen as follows:

Table IV.3. Types of written corrective technology-based feedback

No	Types
1	Direct feedback
2	Indirect feedback
3	Metalinguistic feedback

With direct feedback, the student merely obtains the correct form. To do this, a word, phrase, or morpheme may be deleted, another word, phrase, or morpheme may be added, or the correct form may be written above or near the wrong form. In a direct corrective feedback circumstance, the lecturer provides the student with the proper form. This can take a variety of different forms, such as striking out unnecessary words, phrases, or morphemes, inserting writing the proper form above or near to the incorrect form, and

A Case Study of Technology Based Feedback on Students Assessment during Online Classes

so on. The result of the study shows that this type of feedback could be effective as the time allotment of using this type is shorter than other type of corrective feedback.

Example 1.

Tourism can be defined as a journey from one place to another that is temporary. According to the World Tourism Organization in Istriyani (2021:21) tourism can be ~~definitied~~ ~~defined~~ as a person's travel activity and temporary living outside his usual environment for leisure time, business and other purposes.

Direct corrective feedback has the advantage of providing students with detailed advice on how to correct their errors. If students are unable to self-correct their errors because they are uninformed of the correct form, students could directly know their mistakes. Direct corrective feedback is probably better to indirect corrective feedback when dealing with inexperienced student writers. Although it might help students produce the proper form when they revise their work, because it only requires minimal thought on their part, it might not contribute to long-term learning.

The second type is indirect corrective feedback. This kind of correction provides students with a clear explanation of the types of errors they have made through the use of error codes. Labels are placed above the error in the text's margin to indicate the specific type of error. This still counts as indirect corrective feedback because the students are expected to make the corrections on their own. Indirect corrective feedback consists of pointing out a student's error without actually repairing it. The errors can be highlighted, omissions in the student's writing can be highlighted with cursors (as in the example below), or a cross can be added to the margin adjacent to the line that contains the error. It can be done easily when the task or assignments is in the form of Microsoft words.

Through the use of error codes, this type of correction gives students a clear explanation of the types of mistakes they have done. To identify the precise sort of error, labels are positioned above the location of the error in the text's margin. Indirect corrective feedback entails pointing out a mistake a student has done but not actually fixing it. This can be accomplished by highlighting the mistakes, highlighting omissions in the student's text with cursors (as in the example below), or by adding a cross to the margin next to the line that contains the mistake. Essentially, the decision here is whether or not to show the precise position of the problem.

Example 2.

c. Documentation

According to Sugiyono in Setyaningsari (2020:19) Documentation can be defined is a way used to obtain data and information in the form of books, archives, documents, writing numbers and pictures in the form of reports and information who can support research. For this report, the writer ~~use~~ a photos taken from the area around the Grojogan Sewu waterfall as documentation. The documentation can be seen in

Comment [p1]: Supposed to be in past tense

Because it facilitates "directed learning and problem solving" and encourages students to think about language forms, indirect feedback, as previously stated, is typically favored to direct input. It is believed to have a higher potential of resulting in longterm learning as a result of these elements. The findings of the studies that have looked into this problem, meanwhile, are quite erratic.

The last type is metalinguistic corrective feedback in which it requires that students receive some form of direct feedback on the types of errors they have made. There are two distinct explicit comment types. Error codes are by far the most often used. These are shorter names for various different types of faults. The labels can hide where the error is located in the text or in the margin. In the latter case, the exact location of the problem may or may not be shown. In the former, using the provided clue, the student must determine the necessary correction, but in the latter, identifying the error must come before calculating the necessary correction.

First, collecting data. ~~The writer collects the data by observation, interview and documentation. The writer interview the manager of Grojogan sewu waterfall who a responsibility to managing grojogan sewu waterfall as tourism object then the writer observed the situation there is it already in accordance with the managers. To get more data and information and the writer will take documentation by the picture and location to fit up the data.~~

Comment [p2]: Re Organize

The second type of metalinguistic corrective feedback is providing students with reasons for their errors in metalinguistic terms. The example that comes next is provided. This is much less common, maybe because it takes a lot longer than using error codes and because it requires the lecturer to have sufficient metalinguistic knowledge to be able to write accurate and clear explanations for a variety of errors.

A Case Study of Technology Based Feedback on Students Assessment during Online Classes

5. DISCUSSION

The vast body of research on classroom instruction views feedback as an essential classroom activity. Whether a student's response is correct or incorrect, according to Good and Brophy (2000), lecturers should offer feedback to motivate students by letting them know how they are doing. Some types of feedback may introduce by some experts, the two types that was the focus of this study are oral and written corrective feedback. The research went more specific in feedback that was given during online classes which means focusing on the feedback that was given using technology as the platform. Based on Sheen (2011), oral corrective technology feedback can be categorized as 6 types namely recast, explicit correction, clarification requests, repetition, elicitation, and the last is metalinguistic clue.

The first type that is recast is the most type of oral feedback that was occurred during the online class. It was followed by explicit correction and repetition. Those three type of oral corrective feedback can be delivered directly and the students can catch what the correct way of their errors. The time allotment for giving these three types is shorter than the other three. For the clarification requests, elicitation and metalinguistic clue, the results show that these three types allowed more time allotment as the students cannot get the correct answer directly. As the class was in online platform, the lecturers rarely conducted this feedback.

Based on Sheen (2011), for the written technology feedback is in the three type's namely direct feedback, indirect feedback, and metalinguistic feedback. The most common feedback during online classes is direct feedback and indirect feedback. The result shows that, when the error is not really crucial, for example in punctuation or typo, the lecturers directly gave the correct words. The error will be in the red color and followed by the correct word. Moreover, for indirect feedback, it is given when the error in the form of grammar error. The feedback was given with in the way of the lecturers showed the grammatical error without giving the correct version. For the last type of written corrective feedback, it is the most rarely used as the correct version was given implicitly, that will lead the students need extra time to process what is wrong and how to revise it.

6. CONCLUSION

According to the study's findings, it is possible to draw the following conclusion: Two sorts of feedback were supplied to students during the online teaching and learning process. The lecturers evaluated oral and written corrective feedback, two types of technology-based feedback, before providing comments. When compared to offline classes, the implementation differs significantly in terms of the available time and the platform. There are various sorts of oral technology-based remedial feedback available. Recast, explicit correction, Clarification requests, Repetition, Elicitation, and Metalinguistic hint are some examples of oral corrective feedback. Direct feedback, indirect feedback, and metalinguistic feedback are the three sorts of feedback that may be seen from the written technology-based corrective feedback.

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A Case Study of Technology Based Feedback on Students Assessment during Online Classes

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